

Study protocol for a longitudinal observational cohort study of multimodal visual biomarkers in prodromal, early and moderate Alzheimer's disease: the BegiAlz Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Early detection and monitoring of Alzheimer’s disease (AD) are limited by the lack of scalable, non-invasive tissue-level biomarkers. The retina provides a unique window into central nervous system pathology and may reveal early structural, microvascular, and functional alterations associated with AD pathology.

Objectives: BegiAlz aims to evaluate whether multimodal visual system biomarkers, alone or combined with blood-based AD biomarkers, can improve diagnostic and prognostic stratification across the early AD continuum.

Methods: BegiAlz is a prospective, longitudinal observational cohort study conducted across multiple centers in the Basque Health Service. Participants include individuals with prodromal AD, mild cognitive impairment without AD biomarkers, moderate AD, and cognitively unimpaired controls. Recruitment combines retrospective CSF-based identification and prospective clinical enrollment. Participants undergo baseline, 1-year, and 2-year assessments including clinical and neuropsychological evaluation, visual function testing, retinal imaging (OCT, OCT-A), electrophysiology (ERG), eye-tracking, chromatic pupillometry, and plasma biomarker sampling. Primary outcomes are retinal structural and microvascular measures, electrophysiological responses, visual function, and longitudinal cognitive change. Analyses will adjust for demographic, vascular, and clinical covariates.

Ethics and Dissemination: The study was approved by the Comité de Ética de la Investigación con Medicamentos de Euskadi (CEIm-E; code PI2023126), and all participants provide written informed consent. Results will be disseminated through peer-reviewed publications, conference presentations, and public data sharing when appropriate.

Strengths and Limitations: Strengths include multimodal, longitudinal assessment of retinal and visual biomarkers combined with blood-based AD markers, standardized acquisition protocols, and multicenter recruitment. Limitations include potential missing data, differential test completion, attrition over follow-up, and heterogeneity of baseline disease stages.

BACKGROUND

Alzheimer's disease is now understood as a biological continuum in which molecular pathology develops years before overt dementia [1]. In the prodromal stage, individuals typically present with mild cognitive impairment together with biomarker evidence of AD pathology [2]. Although cerebrospinal fluid and molecular imaging biomarkers have transformed diagnostic precision, they remain invasive, costly, or not easily scalable across routine clinical settings [3]. Blood-based biomarkers have improved accessibility [4], but they do not directly capture tissue-level correlates of neurodegeneration.

The visual system is increasingly recognized as a relevant source of accessible biomarkers in neurodegenerative disease [5, 6]. Visual symptoms and deficits are common in AD and may emerge early in the disease course [7]. The retina, because of its embryological and anatomical relationship with the central nervous system, offers a non-invasive opportunity to assess neuroaxonal structure, microvascular integrity, and neuronal function. Optical coherence tomography and OCT angiography have identified retinal structural and vascular abnormalities in AD [8-22], while electrophysiological and visual function tests may detect dysfunction before overt atrophy becomes evident [23]. However, prior studies have often evaluated these modalities in isolation, have focused on global or parafoveal metrics, and have rarely incorporated contemporary plasma biomarkers.

BegiAlz was therefore conceived as a longitudinal observational cohort study to evaluate multimodal visual biomarkers in prodromal and early AD. The study aims not only to improve diagnostic differentiation but also to determine whether retinal and visual measures track disease progression and molecular biomarker dynamics over time.

HYPOTHESIS AND OBJECTIVES

Hypothesis

We hypothesize that multimodal visual biomarkers can identify early AD-related abnormalities. We further hypothesize that combining visual biomarkers with plasma markers will improve diagnostic stratification, and that longitudinal retinal and visual changes will parallel cognitive and molecular progression.

Primary objectives

1. To assess whether multimodal analysis of the visual system, alone or combined with plasma biomarkers of AD pathology and neurodegeneration, differentiates patients with prodromal AD from cognitively unimpaired controls and from patients with mild cognitive impairment without AD biomarkers.

2. To determine whether baseline visual system biomarkers predict subsequent cognitive decline in prodromal AD.
3. To evaluate whether longitudinal changes in visual biomarkers track molecular and clinical markers of neurodegeneration.

Secondary objectives

5. To map the topographic pattern of retinal structural and microvascular changes across disease stages.
6. To examine relationships between retinal biomarkers, electrophysiological measures, visual function, and cognitive performance.
7. To explore whether multimodal visual biomarkers identify progression gradients extending from prodromal to moderate AD.

STUDY DESIGN AND SETTING

BegiAlz is a two-year longitudinal observational study led by the Biobizkaia Health Research Institute. Participants are assessed at baseline, year 1, and year 2.

Participants are recruited from multiple centers within the Basque Health Service (Osakidetza), including Cruces University Hospital, Urduliz Hospital, and Galdakao Hospital, through a combination of retrospective identification and prospective recruitment. Patients with pAD and MCI are retrospectively identified through the Clinical Analysis Laboratory at Cruces University Hospital, which centralizes routine cerebrospinal fluid biomarker analyses from several hospitals in Bizkaia whereas patients with moderate AD are prospectively identified in outpatient clinics. CSF sampling follows standardized preanalytical and analytical procedures harmonized with the Hospital de Sant Pau protocol [24], and inclusion requires abnormal CSF core AD biomarkers consistent with AD neuropathologic change according to the NIA-AA research framework [25]; Eligible individuals are then clinically reviewed by neurologist co-investigators and invited to participate. Cognitively unimpaired controls are recruited through community-based associations.

The study was launched in 2023. The original protocol was approved in October 2023, and the study is expected to continue until 31 August 2027 to complete the planned longitudinal evaluations.

PARTICIPANTS

The study evaluates multimodal visual system biomarkers (including retinal structural imaging, retinal microvascular imaging, electrophysiology, and visual function) in individuals with

prodromal Alzheimer's disease (pAD), mild cognitive impairment without AD biomarkers (MCI), moderate AD, and cognitively unimpaired controls.

Inclusion criteria

Prodromal Alzheimer's disease

- be aged 50 to 80 years
- meet clinical criteria for mild cognitive impairment attributable to Alzheimer's disease
- show abnormal core AD biomarkers in cerebrospinal fluid, consistent with AD neuropathologic change according to the NIA-AA research framework
- have cerebrospinal fluid sampling performed within the predefined interval before baseline research evaluation

Mild cognitive impairment without AD biomarkers

- be aged 50 to 80 years
- have objective mild cognitive impairment on standardized assessment
- have cerebrospinal fluid AD biomarkers not consistent with AD pathology

Moderate Alzheimer's disease

- have a clinical diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease at a more advanced symptomatic stage than the prodromal group;

Cognitively unimpaired controls

- show no objective cognitive impairment on standardized neuropsychological testing;
- have no history of major neurological or psychiatric disease;
- be frequency-matched to the prodromal AD group by age and sex whenever feasible.

Exclusion criteria

Participants are excluded if they have ophthalmological, neurological, psychiatric, or systemic disorders that may affect retinal structure, visual function, or cognition. Ocular exclusion criteria are applied in accordance with OSCAR-IB quality and interpretability principles [26].

All participants undergo a dedicated ophthalmological screening assessment to confirm eligibility and reduce confounding by ocular disease. Screening includes objective refraction, best-corrected binocular visual acuity, intraocular pressure measurement, and retinal imaging with OCT. Relevant ocular history is recorded, including trauma or surgery, refractive error, cataract, glaucoma, age-related macular degeneration, other retinopathies, and other visual disorders. Structural retinal abnormalities or relevant ocular comorbidities identified during screening will lead to exclusion.

In addition, specific exclusion criteria are applied to reduce confounding by systemic conditions with potential impact on retinal or microvascular measures. These criteria are defined using pragmatic quantitative thresholds and clinical judgement.

- Diabetes mellitus is not an exclusion criterion per se. However, participants are excluded in case of poor metabolic control (HbA1c > 8.0%), evidence of diabetic microangiopathy (e.g., nephropathy or peripheral polyneuropathy), or signs of diabetic retinopathy on ophthalmological evaluation or OCT.
- Arterial hypertension is not an exclusion criterion unless poorly controlled or clinically complicated, defined by persistently elevated blood pressure (e.g., $\geq 160/100$ mmHg) or evidence of relevant hypertension-mediated organ damage.
- Participants are excluded in case of harmful alcohol consumption, defined as a sustained intake of approximately ≥ 4 standard drinks/day in women or ≥ 5 drinks/day in men, or documented alcohol-related systemic disease.
- Heavy tobacco exposure may lead to exclusion when considered likely to affect retinal or vascular measures, typically in cases of current smoking ≥ 20 cigarettes/day over several years or high cumulative exposure (e.g., ≥ 40 pack-years).
- Current or recent (within the previous 12 months) use of illicit psychoactive substances or non-medical stimulant drugs (e.g., cocaine, amphetamines) constitutes an absolute exclusion criterion.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURES

Clinical and Neuropsychological Assessment

Baseline clinical variables included age, sex, general medical history, disease duration, and current medications in participants with pAD. Symptom duration was recorded as the time since onset of cognitive complaints reported by the participant or an informant. Disease duration was established based on the time since diagnosis.

Global cognitive status is assessed using the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) and the Clinical Dementia Rating (CDR). Cognitive performance is further evaluated using the Repeatable Battery for the Assessment of Neuropsychological Status (RBANS), yielding index scores for five cognitive domains and a total composite score. Executive function and processing speed are assessed using the Stroop test and the Trail Making Test (TMT), parts A and B. Depressive symptoms are evaluated using the Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS–Yesavage).

Visual function

Visual function is assessed binocularly using the Precision Vision Visual Acuity Test (PVVAT) digital software (Precision Vision, Woodstock, IL), with a monitor positioned 4 meters away from the patient. Testing is conducted under ambient lighting conditions, with the room light turned off to ensure the luminance at the center of the optotype does not exceed 15 foot-candles.

High-contrast visual acuity (VA) is tested using letter sizes starting at 0.7 logMAR. The patient is asked to identify letters, and the test continued until they correctly identified 3 out of 5 letters on a given line up to -0.3 logMAR. Once this threshold is met, the test stops and the VA in logMAR is recorded, along with the total number of correctly identified letters. Five correctly identified letters corresponded to a logMAR VA of 0.7, whereas 40 letters corresponded to a logMAR VA of 0, with other values calculated proportionally (a reduction of 0.1 logMAR for every 5 correctly identified letters).

Low-contrast VA is assessed with letters of 2.5% contrast and starting at letter size of 0.9 logMAR, and progressing to -0.3 logMAR. As with the high-contrast test, the patient reads the letters until the smallest readable letters were identified. The VA in logMAR is recorded as well as the total number of correctly identified letters. Five correctly identified letters corresponded to a logMAR low-contrast VA of 0.9, whereas 25 letters corresponded to 0.5 logMAR low-contrast VA, and 50 letters to 0 logMAR low-contrast VA (a reduction of 0.1 logMAR for every 5 correctly identified letters).

Contrast sensitivity is evaluated using letters displayed on a digital screen at 4 meters, beginning at 60% contrast and a letter size of 0.8 logMAR. The contrast is systematically reduced in steps of 10% (e.g., 60%, 50%, 40%, etc.) down to 10%. Below 10%, contrast is reduced in 1% decrements until the lowest detectable contrast (1%) was reached. For each contrast level, the number of correctly identified letters is recorded. Both the lowest detectable contrast percentage and the total number of correctly identified letters are recorded. Higher contrast percentage in contrast sensitivity measurements indicates poorer visual function.

Color vision is assessed with Ishihara plates incorporated in PVAAT software and with the Farnsworth D-15 test (Luneau Ophthalmologie). The latter is designed to measure the ability to differentiate colors in a sequence of color chips. The test is conducted under optimal ambient lighting conditions, i.e., near a window to ensure natural lighting, or in well-lit conditions that mimic daylight. The color cups are randomly arranged on the table, and participants were asked to arrange the cups in a way that creates a smooth color gradient using the following instructions: *“You need to arrange these chips in a gradient of color. Each chip should be placed next to the one that most closely resembles its color. For example, a red chip should not be placed next to a blue chip. There is no time limit, and you may make as many adjustments as you like. Please let me know when you have finished.”* The final arrangement of the cups is documented, and their responses are scored based on the total color difference score (TCDS) and Color Confusion Index

(CCI) calculated from <https://www.torok.info/colorvision/d15.htm>. A higher TCDS or CCI indicate greater difficulty in distinguishing colors.

Additional visual and visuocognitive tools include eye-tracking-based testing and computerized visual cognition tasks according to the protocol procedures.

Retinal OCT Acquisition and Processing

Retinal imaging is performed using the Spectralis OCT system (HRA2 Acquisition Module version 6.16.6.0, Heidelberg Engineering, Germany). Macular volumetric scans consist of 25 horizontal B-scans covering a 20° × 20° area, with 512 A-scans per B-scan and 49 frames averaged per B-scan.

Layer segmentation is performed using built-in software. All OCT images fulfilled OSCAR-IB quality criteria [27]. Segmented macular scans were exported in .vol format and processed using the RETIMAT software developed by Mondragon University and IIS Biobizkaia [28].

By default, the average thickness within the foveal zone (central 1-mm diameter disc), parafoveal area (3-mm diameter ring adjacent to the foveal zone), and perifoveal area (3- to 6-mm diameter ring surrounding the parafovea) is computed by averaging the point-by-point thicknesses in each sector, although the system allows flexibility in defining the sectors. The average thicknesses is calculated for the following layer complexes: total retinal thickness (TRT), macular nerve fiber layer (mRNFL), ganglion cell-inner plexiform complex (GCIPL), inner nuclear layer (INL), outer plexiform–Henle fiber–outer nuclear layer (OPL–HF–ONL), and the complex including external limiting membrane, photoreceptor inner and outer segments, retinal pigment epithelium, and Bruch’s membrane (ELM–BM). However, RETIMAT allows flexibility to compute thicknesses based on the individual Spectralis segmentation layers.

OCT Angiography Acquisition and Processing

Macular OCT-A consisted of high-resolution scans with a 10° × 10° scanning area and 512 A-scans per B-scan. TruTrack™ active eye tracking is used to minimize motion artifacts. *En face* OCT-A images are exported as 768 × 768-pixel JPEG files for analysis. OCT-A acquisitions are required to have a quality score of ≥ 30.

The macular region is topographically segmented into a central foveal disc (1-mm diameter) and a surrounding parafoveal ring (2.5-mm diameter). OCT-A metrics are derived using MATLAB-based image processing pipelines, from which vessel density, fractal dimension, and lacunarity of the microvasculature in the superficial and deep vascular complexes (SVC and DVC) are extracted. The tortuosity of microvasculature is also computed. The area and circularity of the foveal avascular zone (FAZ) is also quantified following our previously described methodology [29].

Electroretinography Acquisition and Analysis

Full-field photopic electroretinography (ERG) recordings are performed following International Society for Clinical Electrophysiology of Vision (ISCEV) guidelines [30]. Participants undergo light adaptation for 10 minutes prior to recording. ERG responses are elicited with brief white flashes presented on a photopic background and recorded using DTL fiber electrodes positioned at the lower conjunctival fornix. Signals were band-pass filtered (1–300 Hz), averaged over multiple trials, and analyzed offline.

Two primary ERG parameters are quantified: photopic negative response (phNR) amplitude and phNR implicit time. Only high-quality, artifact-free ERG waveforms will be included in the analyses.

Pupillometry and eye-tracking

Pupillometry is performed using the NeurOptics NPi-200 Pupillometer following a minimum of 2 minutes of dark adaptation to stabilize baseline pupil diameter. Measurements are obtained monocularly under controlled ambient lighting conditions. The protocol consists of a single standardized light stimulus delivered to each eye with an intensity of 50 μ W and a background illumination of 0 μ W. The total recording duration is 5.01 seconds, including a pulse duration of 0.80 seconds.

The following parameters are automatically recorded and analyzed: baseline pupil size, minimum pupil diameter, latency of constriction, constriction velocity (average and maximum), dilation velocity, and percentage of pupil constriction. Each eye is measured once; if the recording is affected by artefacts, the measurement is repeated.

Eye-tracking is performed using the DIVE system under standardized lighting and viewing distance conditions (typically 50–70 cm). Calibration is conducted prior to testing using a multi-point calibration grid to ensure spatial accuracy.

The protocol includes a battery of oculomotor tasks designed to assess multiple domains of visual and neurological function:

- **Fixation tasks (short and long duration):** evaluation of gaze stability, fixation stability (e.g., bivariate contour ellipse area), and fixation duration.
- **Saccadic tasks:** assessment of reflexive and voluntary saccades, including latency, peak velocity, accuracy (gain), and error rates.
- **Smooth pursuit tasks:** evaluation of tracking ability using moving stimuli at controlled velocities, with parameters such as pursuit gain, number of catch-up saccades, and tracking consistency.

Data are sampled at the device's native frequency (typically ≥ 60 Hz) and processed using manufacturer-provided algorithms. Blink artifacts and signal losses are automatically detected and excluded from analysis.

These procedures are intended to capture oculomotor and pupillary dysfunction potentially related to neurodegeneration.

Plasma Collection and Biomarker Quantification

Blood samples were obtained by morning venipuncture using EDTA tubes and processed following a standardized preanalytical protocol harmonized with that used at Hospital de Sant Pau and consistent with current international recommendations for blood-based AD biomarkers [31]. Plasma was isolated by centrifugation at 3500 g for 10 minutes at room temperature, immediately aliquoted, and stored at -80 °C until analysis. All samples were collected within one month of OCT imaging and ERG recordings.

Plasma biomarkers were quantified at the Clinical Analysis Laboratory of Cruces University Hospital using the automated LUMIPULSE G immunoassay platform [32]. Analytes included β -amyloid 1–40 ($A\beta 1-40$), β -amyloid 1–42 ($A\beta 1-42$), phosphorylated tau (p-tau181 and p-tau217), neurofilament light chain (NfL), and glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), as well as derived ratios (e.g., $A\beta 42/40$, p-tau/ $A\beta 42$). All analyses were performed according to the manufacturer's instructions and under strict internal quality-control procedures, in line with published recommendations for analytical validity and inter-laboratory reproducibility of plasma AD biomarkers.

EXPOSURES, OUTCOMES AND COVARIATES

Exposure Variables

The principal disease-related exposures include:

- Study group: participants with prodromal Alzheimer's disease (pAD), mild cognitive impairment (MCI), and moderate AD, as defined in the protocol.
- Biological markers of AD pathology and neurodegeneration, measured in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and plasma.
- CSF core biomarkers: $A\beta 1-42$, $A\beta 1-40$, p-tau181, p-tau217, total tau, and derived ratios.
- Plasma biomarkers: $A\beta 1-40$, $A\beta 1-42$, p-tau181, p-tau217, neurofilament light chain (NfL), glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), and derived ratios (e.g., $A\beta 42/40$, p-tau/ $A\beta 42$)

Primary Outcome Domains

Aligned with the study's objectives, primary outcomes focus on multimodal visual system biomarkers and longitudinal cognitive change:

- **Retinal structural** measures derived from OCT (total retinal thickness, mRNFL, GCIPL, INL, OPL–HF–ONL, ELM–BM).
- **Retinal microvascular** measures derived from OCT-A (vessel density, fractal dimension, lacunarity, tortuosity, foveal avascular zone metrics).
- **Retinal electrophysiological** measures derived from ERG (phNR amplitude and implicit time).
- **Visual function** measures (high- and low-contrast visual acuity, contrast sensitivity, color vision, eye-tracking and pupillometry indices).
- **Cognitive** measures: longitudinal change in MoCA, CDR, RBANS domain and total scores, Stroop test, and Trail Making Test (TMT) performance.

Secondary Outcome Domains

Secondary outcomes provide detailed mapping of visual system changes and multimodal relationships:

- Topographic characterization of retinal structural and microvascular alterations across disease stages.
- Associations between retinal structure, microvasculature, electrophysiology, visual function, and cognitive performance.
- Evaluation of progression patterns from prodromal to moderate AD stages using multimodal biomarkers.

Covariates and Potential Confounders

Prespecified covariates include:

- Demographics: age, sex, years of education.
- Vascular risk factors: summarized in a vascular risk score including hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes mellitus, and current smoking.
- Clinical variables: disease duration, depressive symptoms (GDS), and current medications.

EFFORTS TO ADDRESS BIAS

Several strategies are implemented to minimize potential bias. Recruitment combines multiple centers and both retrospective and prospective approaches, and control participants are

frequency-matched by age and sex whenever feasible. Ophthalmological screening and OCT quality criteria reduce confounding from ocular comorbidities, and all imaging, electrophysiology, and functional assessments follow standardized acquisition protocols. Staff performing assessments are trained and certified to ensure consistency, and instruments are regularly calibrated to maintain measurement reliability across centers and over time. Outcome analyses are conducted with blinding to participant group when feasible, and predefined analysis plans specify handling of missing data and longitudinal trajectories. Follow-up adherence and data completeness are prospectively monitored to mitigate attrition-related bias. Planned multivariable analyses adjust for key demographic, vascular, and clinical covariates. These measures collectively aim to enhance the internal validity and reproducibility of findings in this real-world observational cohort.

STUDY SAMPLE SIZE

Sample size was determined to ensure adequate statistical power for the study's primary objectives: (i) detecting cross-sectional differences between prodromal Alzheimer's disease (AD) and cognitively unimpaired controls using retinal biomarkers, and (ii) evaluating the longitudinal association between baseline visual biomarkers and cognitive decline.

For cross-sectional comparisons, estimation was conservatively based on structural retinal measures obtained by optical coherence tomography (OCT), as these show smaller effect sizes than vascular retinal parameters. Meta-analyses report standardized mean differences (SMDs) in the range of -0.30 to -0.46 for key structural metrics, including peripapillary retinal nerve fiber layer (pRNFL; SMD ≈ -0.32) and ganglion cell–inner plexiform layer (GC-IPL; SMD ≈ -0.46) thickness in mild cognitive impairment compared to controls[33, 34]. In contrast, retinal vascular measures derived from OCT-angiography demonstrate larger effect sizes (e.g., reductions in vessel density in superficial and deep capillary plexuses), indicating that studies based on vascular parameters would require smaller sample sizes[35]. Therefore, to ensure a conservative and robust design, sample size calculations were based on structural retinal thickness measures. Assuming a small-to-moderate effect size (Cohen's $d \approx 0.40$), a two-tailed independent samples t-test with $\alpha = 0.05$ and 80% power yields an estimated requirement of approximately 80–100 participants per group. This assumption is justified by selecting an effect size toward the upper range of published estimates while remaining within empirically supported bounds for prodromal AD populations.

For longitudinal analyses, available evidence indicates moderate associations between baseline retinal structure and subsequent cognitive decline in neurodegenerative diseases[36, 37]. Large cohort studies report hazard ratios of approximately 1.4–1.7 per standard deviation decrease in retinal thickness[38], while correlations with cognitive trajectories are generally in the range of $r \approx 0.20$ – 0.35 when conservatively summarized across heterogeneous populations[39, 40]. Based

on these estimates, multiple linear regression models (assuming up to 5–7 predictors and $\alpha = 0.05$) require approximately 75–95 participants to detect significant associations with 80% power.

Assuming an attrition rate of approximately 10% over the follow-up period, the target sample size is adjusted accordingly. Therefore, the study aims to recruit approximately 90 participants per group to ensure adequate power for both cross-sectional and longitudinal analyses after accounting for dropouts. With four groups (prodromal AD, MCI without AD biomarkers, moderate AD, and cognitively unimpaired controls), the total planned sample size is approximately 360 participants.

Sample size calculations were performed using standard power analysis software (G*Power (version 3.1), and cross-validated using regression-based approaches implemented in R.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS PLAN

Baseline characteristics will be summarized by study group using means and standard deviations or medians and interquartile ranges for continuous variables, and counts with percentages for categorical variables. Between-group comparisons will use t-tests or ANOVA for normally distributed data, and non-parametric tests (e.g., Mann–Whitney U or Kruskal–Wallis) when distributions are skewed. Categorical variables will be compared using chi-square or Fisher’s exact tests.

Longitudinal trajectories of visual and cognitive outcomes will be analyzed using linear mixed-effects models (LMMs), which account for within-subject correlations over repeated measures and allow for inclusion of participants with incomplete follow-up. LMMs will include fixed effects for time, group, and relevant covariates (age, sex, years of education, vascular risk score), with random intercepts and slopes as appropriate. For outcomes with non-normal distributions, generalized linear mixed-effects models (GLMMs) will be employed. Alternatively, generalized estimating equations (GEE) may be used, specifying an appropriate working correlation structure.

Associations between baseline biomarkers (retinal structural and vascular measures, electrophysiology, visual function, plasma biomarkers) and longitudinal cognitive change will be examined within LMM or other regression frameworks, incorporating interaction terms to test whether biomarker trajectories differ by diagnostic group. Multiplicity arising from multiple visual and molecular biomarkers will be addressed using false discovery rate control or other prespecified family-wise error correction methods.

Missing data will be reported for each variable and visit. LMMs and GEE naturally accommodate some missingness under a missing-at-random assumption. Sensitivity analyses will explore the impact of alternative missing data mechanisms, such as multiple imputation or complete-case analysis. Subgroup analyses may be performed to compare diagnostic categories, disease stages, or biomarker-defined strata.

All analyses will be conducted using validated statistical software (R or SPSS), with two-tailed significance set at $\alpha = 0.05$ unless otherwise specified.

PATIENT AND PUBLIC INVOLVEMENT

Control participants are recruited through community-based associations, which facilitates community engagement with the study. Formal patient and public involvement in protocol design was not established as a separate methodological component.

ETHICS AND DISSEMINATION

The study complies with the Declaration of Helsinki and applicable Spanish biomedical research regulations. It was approved by the Comité de Ética de la Investigación con Medicamentos de Euskadi under code PI2023126. A later favorable ethical opinion approved protocol version v2 dated 17 December 2024 for expansion of cohorts. Written informed consent is obtained from all participants before any research-specific procedures.

Study results will be disseminated through scientific publications, conference presentations, doctoral and academic outputs, and, when appropriate, public deposition of protocol-related documents and metadata.

STUDY STATUS

The study began in 2023 as a three-visit longitudinal observational cohort following funding through the BIOEF Alzheimer research call 2022 (grant BIO22/ALZ/003). The first protocol amendment, approved in early 2025, expanded the cohort to include moderate AD and additional controls. In October 2025, the study duration was formally extended until 31 August 2027 to allow completion of all planned baseline, year 1, and year 2 evaluations.

This document corresponds to protocol version 1.0 (March 2026). Any future amendments will be documented and updated versions will be deposited in Zenodo with version control.

DISCUSSION

BegiAlz is designed to address a clinically relevant gap: the lack of scalable, non-invasive tissue-level biomarkers for early Alzheimer's disease. Its main conceptual strength is the integration of multimodal visual system measurements with contemporary blood-based biomarkers in a longitudinal framework. By incorporating structural, vascular, electrophysiological, and functional measures, the study is expected to provide a richer account of how retinal and visual abnormalities relate to AD biology and progression.

The study also has strengths. It recruits from routine neurology pathways across several hospitals, uses widely available ophthalmic technologies, and applies repeated measures at baseline, year 1, and year 2. These features enable both cross-sectional and longitudinal assessments and may improve translational relevance if specific biomarker combinations prove diagnostically or prognostically useful. Ophthalmological screening and OCT quality control further reduce confounding from ocular comorbidities, while recruitment that combines retrospective CSF-based identification with prospective clinical enrollment across multiple centers enhances generalizability.

At the same time, several limitations should be considered. As a real-world observational cohort, some analyses may be constrained by missing data, differential completion of specific tests, and participant attrition over follow-up. Certain procedures, including detailed imaging or electrophysiology, may yield analyzable data only in subsets of participants. Differences in baseline disease stage, heterogeneity of clinical populations, and variable longitudinal adherence may complicate interpretation. These limitations should be transparently addressed in all downstream analyses and reporting.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The BegiAlz study protocol is publicly available through Zenodo. De-identified data and metadata may be made available upon reasonable request and subject to applicable ethical and data protection regulations. Structured datasets and analysis scripts will be shared in accordance with FAIR data principles whenever possible.

REFERENCES

[1] Jia J, Ning Y, Chen M, Wang S, Yang H, Li F, et al. Biomarker Changes during 20 Years Preceding Alzheimer’s Disease. *N Engl J Med.* 2024;390:712-22.

- [2] Vos SJ, Verhey F, Frolich L, Kornhuber J, Wiltfang J, Maier W, et al. Prevalence and prognosis of Alzheimer's disease at the mild cognitive impairment stage. *Brain*. 2015;138:1327-38.
- [3] Frisoni GB, Hansson O, Nichols E, Garibotto V, Schindler SE, van der Flier WM, et al. New landscape of the diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease. *Lancet*. 2025;406:1389-407.
- [4] Teunissen CE, Verberk IMW, Thijssen EH, Vermunt L, Hansson O, Zetterberg H, et al. Blood-based biomarkers for Alzheimer's disease: towards clinical implementation. *Lancet Neurol*. 2022;21:66-77.
- [5] Hart de Ruyter FJ, Evers M, Morrema THJ, Dijkstra AA, den Haan J, Twisk JWR, et al. Neuropathological hallmarks in the post-mortem retina of neurodegenerative diseases. *Acta Neuropathol*. 2024;148:24.
- [6] Jackson GR, Owsley C. Visual dysfunction, neurodegenerative diseases, and aging. *Neurol Clin*. 2003;21:709-28.
- [7] Alvite-Pineiro T, Lopez-Lopez M, Regueiro U, Pias-Peleteiro JM, Sobrino T, Lema I. Visual Function in Alzheimer's Disease: Current Understanding and Potential Mechanisms Behind Visual Impairment. *J Clin Med*. 2025;14.
- [8] Kim JI, Kang BH. Decreased retinal thickness in patients with Alzheimer's disease is correlated with disease severity. *PLoS ONE*. 2019;14.
- [9] Kim HM, Han JW, Park YJ, Bae JB, Woo SJ, Kim KW. Association Between Retinal Layer Thickness and Cognitive Decline in Older Adults. *JAMA Ophthalmology*. 2022;140:683-90.
- [10] Mutlu U, Colijn JM, Ikram MA, Bonnemaier PWM, Licher S, Wolters FJ, et al. Association of Retinal Neurodegeneration on Optical Coherence Tomography with Dementia: A Population-Based Study. *JAMA Neurology*. 2018;75:1256-63.
- [11] Coppola G, Di Renzo A, Ziccardi L, Martelli F, Fadda A, Manni G, et al. Optical coherence tomography in Alzheimer's disease: A meta-analysis. *PLoS ONE*. 2015;10.
- [12] Marziani E, Pomati S, Ramolfo P, Cigada M, Giani A, Mariani C, et al. Evaluation of retinal nerve fiber layer and ganglion cell layer thickness in Alzheimer's disease using spectral-domain optical coherence tomography. *Investigative Ophthalmology and Visual Science*. 2013;54:5953-8.

- [13] Cipollini V, Abdolrahimzadeh S, Troili F, de Carolis A, Calafiore S, Scuderi L, et al. Neurocognitive Assessment and Retinal Thickness Alterations in Alzheimer Disease: Is There a Correlation? *Journal of Neuro-Ophthalmology*. 2020;40:370-7.
- [14] Ko F, Muthy ZA, Gallacher J, Sudlow C, Rees G, Yang Q, et al. Association of Retinal Nerve Fiber Layer Thinning with Current and Future Cognitive Decline: A Study Using Optical Coherence Tomography. *JAMA Neurology*. 2018;75:1198-205.
- [15] Kwapong WR, Wu N, Lin W, Shen J, Wang Y, Qian J, et al. Retinal microvascular alterations in Alzheimer's disease: Linking blood plasma biomarkers and cerebral small vessel pathology. *Alzheimer's and Dementia*. 2025;21.
- [16] Corradetti G, Oncel D, Kadomoto S, Arakaki X, Klöner RA, Sadun AA, et al. Choriocapillaris and Retinal Vascular Alterations in Presymptomatic Alzheimer's Disease. *Investigative Ophthalmology and Visual Science*. 2024;65.
- [17] Chua J, Hu Q, Ke M, Tan B, Hong J, Yao X, et al. Retinal microvasculature dysfunction is associated with Alzheimer's disease and mild cognitive impairment. *Alzheimer's Research and Therapy*. 2020;12.
- [18] Ma X, Xie Z, Wang H, Tian Z, Bi Y, Li Y, et al. A cross-sectional study of retinal vessel changes based on optical coherence tomography angiography in Alzheimer's disease and mild cognitive impairment. *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience*. 2023;15.
- [19] Jin Q, Lei Y, Wang R, Wu H, Ji K, Ling L. A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Retinal Microvascular Features in Alzheimer's Disease. *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience: Frontiers Media S.A.*; 2021.
- [20] Chen Z, He HL, Qi Z, Bi S, Yang H, Chen X, et al. Cerebral Amyloid Deposition With 18F-Florbetapir PET Mediates Retinal Vascular Density and Cognitive Impairment in Alzheimer's Disease. *Human Brain Mapping*. 2025;46.
- [21] Ibrahim Y, Macerollo A, Sardone R, Shen Y, Romano V, Zheng Y. Retinal microvascular density and inner thickness in Alzheimer's disease and mild cognitive impairment. *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience*. 2025;17.
- [22] Zhang YS, Zhou N, Knoll BM, Samra S, Ward MR, Weintraub S, et al. Parafoveal vessel loss and correlation between peripapillary vessel density and cognitive performance in amnesic mild

cognitive impairment and early Alzheimer's Disease on optical coherence tomography angiography. *PLoS ONE*. 2019;14.

[23] Asanad S, Felix CM, Fantini M, Harrington MG, Sadun AA, Karanjia R. Retinal ganglion cell dysfunction in preclinical Alzheimer's disease: an electrophysiologic biomarker signature. *Scientific Reports*. 2021;11.

[24] Alcolea D, Clarimon J, Carmona-Iragui M, Illan-Gala I, Morenas-Rodriguez E, Barroeta I, et al. The Sant Pau Initiative on Neurodegeneration (SPIN) cohort: A data set for biomarker discovery and validation in neurodegenerative disorders. *Alzheimers Dement (N Y)*. 2019;5:597-609.

[25] Jack CR, Jr., Andrews JS, Beach TG, Buracchio T, Dunn B, Graf A, et al. Revised criteria for diagnosis and staging of Alzheimer's disease: Alzheimer's Association Workgroup. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2024;20:5143-69.

[26] Tewarie P, Balk L, Costello F, Green A, Martin R, Schippling S, et al. The OSCAR-IB consensus criteria for retinal OCT quality assessment. *PLoS One*. 2012;7:e34823.

[27] Tewarie P, Balk L, Costello F, Green A, Martin R, Schippling S, et al. The OSCAR-IB consensus criteria for retinal OCT quality assessment. *PLoS ONE*2012.

[28] Romero-Bascones D, Murueta-Goyena A, Wagner S, Struyven R, Williamson D, Keane P, et al. RETIMAT: an open-source software for retinal OCT image analysis. *Investigative Ophthalmology & Visual Science*. 2023;64:2923-.

[29] Murueta-Goyena A, Barrenechea M, Erramuzpe A, Teijeira-Portas S, Pengo M, Ayala U, et al. Foveal Remodeling of Retinal Microvasculature in Parkinson's Disease. *Front Neurosci*. 2021;15:708700.

[30] Frishman L, Sustar M, Kremers J, McAnany JJ, Sarossy M, Tzekov R, et al. ISCEV extended protocol for the photopic negative response (PhNR) of the full-field electroretinogram. *Doc Ophthalmol*. 2018;136:207-11.

[31] Suarez-Calvet M, Abdelnour C, Alcolea D, Mendioroz-Iriarte M, Balasa M, Morenas-Rodriguez E, et al. Blood-based biomarkers for Alzheimer's disease: positioning document and usage recommendations from the Behavioral Neurology and Dementia Study Group of the Spanish Society of Neurology. *Neurologia (Engl Ed)*. 2025;40:700-12.

- [32] Arranz J, Zhu N, Rubio-Guerra S, Rodriguez-Baz I, Ferrer R, Carmona-Iragui M, et al. Diagnostic performance of plasma pTau(217), pTau(181), Abeta(1-42) and Abeta(1-40) in the LUMIPULSE automated platform for the detection of Alzheimer disease. *Alzheimers Res Ther.* 2024;16:139.
- [33] Ge YJ, Xu W, Ou YN, Qu Y, Ma YH, Huang YY, et al. Retinal biomarkers in Alzheimer's disease and mild cognitive impairment: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ageing Res Rev.* 2021;69:101361.
- [34] Chan VTT, Sun Z, Tang S, Chen LJ, Wong A, Tham CC, et al. Spectral-Domain OCT Measurements in Alzheimer's Disease: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Ophthalmology.* 2019;126:497-510.
- [35] Hui J, Zhao Y, Yu S, Liu J, Chiu K, Wang Y. Detection of retinal changes with optical coherence tomography angiography in mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease patients: A meta-analysis. *PLoS One.* 2021;16:e0255362.
- [36] Murueta-Goyena A, Romero-Bascones D, Teijeira-Portas S, Urcola JA, Ruiz-Martinez J, Del Pino R, et al. Association of retinal neurodegeneration with the progression of cognitive decline in Parkinson's disease. *NPJ Parkinsons Dis.* 2024;10:26.
- [37] Murueta-Goyena A, Del Pino R, Galdos M, Arana B, Acera M, Carmona-Abellan M, et al. Retinal Thickness Predicts the Risk of Cognitive Decline in Parkinson Disease. *Ann Neurol.* 2021;89:165-76.
- [38] Mutlu U, Colijn JM, Ikram MA, Bonnemaier PWM, Licher S, Wolters FJ, et al. Association of Retinal Neurodegeneration on Optical Coherence Tomography With Dementia: A Population-Based Study. *JAMA Neurol.* 2018;75:1256-63.
- [39] Zhang JR, Cao YL, Li K, Wang F, Wang YL, Wu JJ, et al. Correlations between retinal nerve fiber layer thickness and cognitive progression in Parkinson's disease: A longitudinal study. *Parkinsonism Relat Disord.* 2021;82:92-7.
- [40] Ward DD, Mauschitz MM, Bonniger MM, Merten N, Finger RP, Breteler MMB. Association of retinal layer measurements and adult cognitive function: A population-based study. *Neurology.* 2020;95:e1144-e52.